

Bamboo Fibre Extraction and Its Reinforced Polymer Composite Material

Authors : P. Zakikhani, R. Zahari, M. T. H. Sultan, D. L. Majid

Abstract : Natural plant fibres reinforced polymeric composite materials have been used in many fields of our lives to save the environment. Especially, bamboo fibres due to its environmental sustainability, mechanical properties, and recyclability have been utilized as reinforced polymer matrix composite in construction industries. In this review study bamboo structure and three different methods such as mechanical, chemical and combination of mechanical and chemical to extract fibres from bamboo are summarized. Each extraction method has been done base on the application of bamboo. In addition Bamboo fibre is compared with glass fibre from various aspects and in some parts it has advantages over the glass fibre.

Keywords : bamboo fibres, natural fibres, bio composite, mechanical extraction, glass fibres

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